

Space-time as a physical object. Einstein's testament

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Abstract

In the 1960s physicists were occupied with the question: "Are Einstein's equations applicable to large fields?" For the past few years diligently the where study the literature, including the work of Einstein himself, covering a period of doubt, insight and doubt again in the creation of general relativity and the realization of what has been done.

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1. Introduction

I have lived long enough to remember well that in the 1960s physicists were occupied with the question: "Are Einstein's equations applicable to large fields?" For the past few years I have been diligently studying the literature, including the work of Einstein himself, covering a period of doubt, insight and doubt again in the creation of general relativity and the realization of what has been done.

2. Development

In Einstein's special theory of relativity, the speed of light is independent of the frame of reference.

$$s^2 = (x_1 - x_0)^2 + (y_1 - y_0)^2 + (z_1 - z_0)^2 - c^2(t_1 - t_0)^2$$

is a generalization of the Pythagorean theorem. The value of s does not change if the coordinates are changed according to the Lorentz transformation recipe. Here, for the first time, space is considered as an independent physical object. Minkowski owns the words:

"From now on, time itself and space itself become an empty fiction, and only their unity preserves the chance for reality." (Minkowski) [1]

The next step was taken by Einstein in 1907. The connection between time and acceleration in accelerated reference systems is found and the principle of equivalence of accelerated reference systems and systems with a gravitational field is established. For several years, Einstein accumulated separate results on the relativistic properties of gravity. Perhaps the most important result was the conclusion that the presence of a gravitational field changes the speed of light, i.e. the speed of light is not a constant depends on the gravitational potential. This makes it impossible to describe gravity in Minkowski space. The natural way out of this situation is the transition to the curvilinear Riemann space. Fortunately, by that time, the creation of a mathematical apparatus for calculating the parameters of such a space, tensor analysis (absolute differential calculus), had been completed. Einstein resorts to the help of his friend, the mathematician Grossman, and they

This makes it impossible to describe the movement of bodies using coordinates and a single time, independent of the speed of these bodies. In this case, the spatial and temporal scales change when moving from one uniformly moving (inertial) frame of reference to another.

Already in the special theory of relativity, we see that this is a law of nature that describes the ratio of the scales of space and time, but not "weighty bodies". Time is on a par with space here. Hermann Minkowski took advantage of this and introduced time t as the Euclidean three-dimensional space with coordinates (x, y, z) as an additional, fourth dimension [1]. In Minkowski space, [1] the interval between events

publish the basic principles for constructing a relativistic theory of gravity (general relativity). It also outlines the basics of tensor analysis. [1]

Here it is already necessary to quote the words of Einstein, formulating the subject of the theory of relativity as the study of the physical properties of space [2]:

"When it is said here about the ether, then, of course, it does not mean the corporeal ether of the mechanical wave theory, which obeys the laws of Newtonian mechanics and whose individual points are assigned speed. This theoretical notion with the creation of the special theory of relativity, in my opinion, finally disappeared from the scene. On the contrary, we are talking about those physically conceivable real things that, along with weighty matter, consisting of electrical elementary particles, play a role in the structure of the causal relationships of physics. Therefore, instead of the word "ether" one can just as well say "the physical properties of space". In this case, of course, it would be possible to express the opinion that all objects of physics fall under this concept, since, according to consistent field theory, weighty matter or its constituent elementary

particles should also be considered as a special kind of “field”, or special “states of space”. However, one has to admit that in the present state of physics such an idea is premature, since until now all the efforts of theoretical physicists directed towards this goal have failed. Thus, we are now effectively forced to distinguish between “matter” and “fields”, although we can hope that future generations will overcome this dualistic view and replace it with a single concept, as the field theory of our days has tried in vain to do”. (Einstein, 1966) [2]

Modern evidence confirms that space is indeed not flat. The most convincing evidence of this is the experiment to detect the delay of an electromagnetic signal in a gravitational field, discovered by the group of Irwin Shapiro. Subsequent more accurate observations of close relativistic star systems proved that space is not flat - in the presence of a gravitational field, the Pythagorean theorem does not work.

It should be added that the well-known unshieldability of the gravitational field makes the physical space so unusual that attempts to attribute properties of ordinary matter or (quantum) fields to gravity do not look convincing.

3. Einstein's latest work

Now cite the opinion of the creator (it is difficult to resist the temptation to capitalize this word), expressed in his last published work (Appendix II) to the fifth edition of the book *The Essences of the Theory of Relativity*. At the end of the article, Einstein warns against unreasonable expansion of the theory [3]:

“General remarks A.:

From my point of view, the theory presented here is logically the simplest relativistic field theory possible at all. But this does not mean that nature cannot be subject to more complex field theories. More complex field theories have often been proposed. They can be classified according to the following characteristics.

a) Increase in the number of dimensions of the continuum. In this case, it is necessary to explain why the continuum is obviously limited to four dimensions;

b) Introduction of fields of a different kind (for example, a vector field) in addition to the displacement field and the tensor field g_{ik} (or g^{ik}); c) Introduction of field equations of higher order (in the sense of differentiation).

In my opinion, such more complex theories and their combinations should be considered only if there are physical reasons based on experiment for this”. (Einstein, 1966) [3]

Are there any physical reasons for such research? Rather, on the contrary, the theory receives more and more confirmations, there are no disagreements with observations. Against this background, numerous attempts to expand the theory do not look convincing. The variety of approaches rather speaks of the absence of the very, only correct transition to a new theory.

General relativity can be compared to a capricious lady trying on outfits and trying to pull on fashionable outfits from someone else's shoulder. I will allow myself to express surprise at the consideration of quantum fields of particles endowed with the ability to interact with matter. This contradicts the observed transparency of matter for the gravitational field. The shading of the gravitational field by the Moon would lead to catastrophes on Earth. In addition, we would observe daily morning and evening tsunamis if such shading took place. In general, attributing the properties of ordinary matter to the gravitational field does not seem reasonable. Speaking of the ether as a degree of the materiality of space, Einstein says:

“According to the general theory of relativity, space is inconceivable without ether; indeed, in such a space, not only would the propagation of light be impossible, but scales and clocks could not exist, and there would be no space-time distances in the physical sense of the word. However, this ether cannot be imagined as consisting of parts traceable in time;

only weighty matter has this property; in the same way, the concept of motion cannot be applied to it". (Einstein, 1966) [2, 3]

When expanding the general theory of relativity, it is necessary to take into account the fact that the curvature of space is an observable fact. Therefore, the introduction of quantum fields in Euclidean space seems rather frivolous. Going back to Einstein's latest work. Einstein goes on to talk about the need to rid the theory of singularities [5]:

"B. The field theory is not yet completely determined by the system of field equations. Should we recognize the existence of singularities? Should boundary conditions be postulated? As regards the first question, my opinion is the following: singularities must be ruled out. It does not seem reasonable to me to introduce into the continuum theory points (or lines, etc.) for which the field equations do not hold. Moreover, introducing singularities is equivalent to postulating boundary conditions (arbitrary in terms of field equations) on the "surfaces" surrounding the singularities. Without such a postulate, the theory would be too vague. The answer to the second question, in my opinion, is that the postulation of boundary conditions is mandatory ..." [5]

It is noteworthy that almost immediately after Einstein's death, in 1958, David Finkelstein identified the Schwarzschild surface as an event horizon, "an ideal unidirectional membrane: causal influences can cross it in only one direction." At the same time, from the point of view of pure mathematics, the Schwarzschild surface does not belong to the original metric space - the metric on this surface and inside it simply does not exist, i.e. is not a solution to the Einstein equation.

Einstein spoke more about the problems of the theory and possible ways of its development in his last work [5]:

"B. Is it possible to think that field theory will make it possible to understand the atomistic and quantum

structure of reality? Almost everyone will answer "no" to this question. But I believe that no one knows for sure about this at the present time, since we do not know how and to what extent the elimination of singularities reduces the set of solutions. We have no method at all for systematically obtaining singularity-free solutions." [5]

There is no need to comment on what has been said, since the situation has not changed over the past time. The general theory of relativity has remained the same. Let's go back to Einstein's equation. Undoubtedly, this is the pinnacle of a brilliant theory. But Einstein, during two years of hard work, failed to include the energy of the gravitational field in the equation, which, according to Einstein, must certainly be present in the field equation [2]:

"Therefore, the gravitational equations take the form

$$\Delta_{\mu\nu}(\gamma) = \kappa(\theta_{\mu\nu} + \vartheta_{\mu\nu})$$

These equations satisfy the requirement, in our opinion, obligatory for the relativistic theory of gravitation; namely, they show that the gravitational field tensor $\vartheta_{\mu\nu}$ is the source of the field along with the tensor of material systems $\theta_{\mu\nu}$. The exclusive position of the energy of the gravitational field in comparison with all other types of energy would lead to unacceptable consequences." [2]

4. Conclusion

However, Einstein failed to complete this program. From the Einstein equation follows only the law of conservation, the law of conservation of energy and momentum of matter (together with the electromagnetic field) in the absence of a gravitational field¹. According to Landau and Lifshitz¹, the exclusion of the gravitational field energy from the Einstein equation is justified because:

"Gravitational interaction plays a role only for bodies with a sufficiently

large mass (due to the smallness of the gravitational constant).” [4]

It is clear that this condition is not suitable for problems with a high value of the field energy density [4].

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